

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING PHONETICS OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT SCHOOL

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Abstract. Sound matter is the main element of speech, and auditory skills are the basis of all types of speech activity. Therefore, to form the skills of oral speech, listening, writing and reading, it is not enough only to be able to pronounce the appropriate sounds, but you should also know how they connect in words, and how these words connect in a sentence. In young children, this happens simultaneously, simply and easily, since this process is carried out in a natural language environment familiar to them. In a non-linguistic environment, that is, in a foreign language lesson, significant attention should be paid to the formulation of pronunciation skills.

Key words: element of speech, auditory skills, types of speech activity, sounds, combinations, speech, accentuation, correct intonation, syntactic constructions.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ФОНЕТИКЕ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА В ШКОЛЕ

Аннотация. Звуковая материя является основным элементом речи, а слуховые навыки – основой всех видов речевой деятельности. Поэтому для формирования навыков устной речи, аудирования, письма и чтения недостаточно только уметь произносить соответствующие звуки, но следует также знать, как они соединяются в словах, и как эти слова соединяются в предложении. У детей раннего возраста это происходит одновременно, просто и легко, поскольку этот процесс осуществляется в привычной для них естественной языковой среде. В неязыковой среде, то есть на уроке иностранного языка, значительное внимание следует уделять формированию навыков произношения.

Ключевые слова: элемент речи, слуховые навыки, виды речевой деятельности, звуки, сочетания, речь, акцентуация, правильная интонация, синтаксические конструкции.

Phonetic skills are automated pronunciation skills, i.e. the skills of pronouncing foreign sounds and their combinations, highlighting these sounds in the flow of sounding speech, accentuation, correct intonation of syntactic constructions of a foreign language. Phonetic skills are also included as automated components in the skills of speaking, listening, reading and writing, i.e. in receptive and reproductive types of speech activity.

Phonetic skills are divided into two large groups: auditory and rhythmic-intonation skills. Auditory-speaking skills, in turn, are divided into auditory (auditory) and actually pronounceable.

Auditory-speaking skills are understood as skills in which all sounds in the speech stream are pronounced phonemically correctly, as well as understanding of all sounds when listening to the speech of others.

Auditory or auditory skills involve actions and operations to recognize and distinguish individual phonemes, words, semantic syntagmas, sentences, etc. [4,17]

Pronunciation skills involve the ability to correctly articulate sounds and connect them in words, phrases and sentences. Sentences, in turn, require proper stress, pause, and intonation.

Modern person in the era of globalization can become a full participant in intercultural communication only through the comprehensive development of foreign language communicative

competence in the learning process, which includes such basic foreign language competencies as linguistic, speech, socio-cultural, compensatory and educational-cognitive [N. Popova, 2021.p.23]. However, the development of these competencies does not always occur in the same way. For some of them, in particular the auditory one, which is part of the speech competence, more thorough methodological development is required. Many Russian scientists have expressed the opinion that it is particularly difficult to teach listening skills, since these skills are partly considered "passive" skills, the results of which cannot be called highly visual and easily assessable [N. Goncharova, 2017.p.]. In turn, in the context of intercultural interaction of people, communication in a foreign language comes to the fore, where listening skills become one of the main skills [S. Elovskaya, 2013.p.33].

Listening is a reactive type of speech activity (as opposed to proactive ones (such as writing and speaking). The purpose of such activity is the direct disclosure of semantic connections and understanding of the incoming speech message. The form of this type of speech activity is uneven, internal. The subject of listening is another person's thought encoded in an audio text. At the same time, the product of this specific type of activity is realized in another type of activity and, according to scientists, acts as a response: comprehension of the semantic content is expressed in non-verbal (information taken into account) and verbal behavior (verbal reaction to what is heard). This judgment confirms the connection between listening and speaking as types of speech activity and indicates the need for parallel training of their skills. In addition, being a receptive type of speech activity, listening develops on a par with reading, and

It involves making connections between auditory and visual images of the word, which can be difficult in the process of learning activities.

The ability to perceive a foreign language significantly affects the overall literacy of the student, mastering the skills of oral speech in a foreign language, in particular English. Thanks to the spread of the Internet, various authentic audio materials have become available for use in teaching foreign languages. This type of materials is more effective than texts in modern teaching materials, as they prepare students for real communication and a real pronunciation picture of the world that schoolchildren will face.

The increasing requirements for the level of proficiency in a foreign language and the change in learning goals necessitate the search for more effective technologies and teaching methods. Auditory means of an authentic nature contribute to the development of phonetic and listening skills among students, allow them to create situations that motivate students to carry out intercultural interaction, taking into account the communicative situation and the norms of speech communication of speakers of different cultures. Thus, authentic audio or video recordings (podcasts), according to M. V. Razumova it can be used to increase motivation to learn foreign languages and develop the skills of monologue and dialogic speech in the context of positioning English as the language of international communication [M. V. Razumova, 2017.p.162]. All this testifies in favor of the inclusion of authentic information technologies as a means of forming the phonetic competence of students in the learning process.

The importance of further research at this stage is determined by the incomplete study of the use of authentic audio text for the formation of phonetic foreign language competence of secondary school students. A preliminary analysis of the English language teaching materials gives

reason to conclude that, despite the active use of auditory means in the educational process, audio and video recording are not considered as a means, and the technology of working with them is not offered.

Thus, the study of scientific literature on this problem and a preliminary analysis of the leading foreign language teaching materials allows us to formulate a conclusion that in the process of developing listening skills, students learn to understand foreign language speech with all its features and qualitative characteristics using a variety of authentic audio and video materials.

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